

Government Support and Entrepreneurial Development in Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigates the influence of government support on entrepreneurial development in Oyo State, Nigeria, aiming to evaluate the effects of financial aid, training initiatives, and regulatory support on small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). The study employs the Resource-Based View (RBV) and Institutional Theory to address a knowledge gap about the role of government interventions in fostering entrepreneurial growth. A descriptive research methodology was utilised, utilising a standardised questionnaire disseminated to proprietors and administrators of SMEs throughout all three senatorial districts of Oyo State. In 2021, the Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN) reported a total of 31,739 SMEs within the population. A multi-stage sampling method was employed to determine a sample size of 1,300 SMEs. A pilot study involving 130 SMEs across ten LGAs in Lagos State yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.81, confirming the validity and reliability of the research instruments. The model summary suggests an R² of 0.951, suggesting that these factors explain approximately 95.1% of the variance in entrepreneurial development. The findings demonstrate that financial aid, training programmes, and regulatory support greatly enhance entrepreneurial development. The research suggests that fostering entrepreneurial development in Oyo State necessitates robust governmental support. Officials are recommended to enhance and sustain support programmes to bolster the entrepreneurial ecosystem in the region.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial development, Financial aid, Government support, Small and medium-sized enterprises, Training initiatives.

1.0 Introduction

1.1 Background

Entrepreneurial development has become an essential element of global economic strategy, as governments increasingly recognise its role in fostering innovation, generating employment, and driving economic growth. This essay analyses global, regional, and local perspectives on governmental support for promoting entrepreneurial development, with a particular focus on Nigeria. The importance of state support for entrepreneurship is well-documented on an international scale. The Small Business Administration (SBA) in the United States is essential in

offering vital assistance to small enterprises and entrepreneurs. The SBA, established in 1953, provides financial support, training, and regulatory guidance to foster the success and growth of small enterprises (U.S. Small Business Administration, 2021). The SBA offers crucial assistance to start-ups by providing loans, grants, and counselling services, which are necessary for their survival and development. Similarly, the European Union has made substantial investments in fostering entrepreneurship through projects such as Horizon Europe. This programme, succeeding Horizon 2020, is designed to fund research and innovation activities aimed at fostering economic growth and addressing societal issues (European Commission, 2022). These global instances illustrate the significant impact that structured governmental support can exert on entrepreneurial success and innovation.

In the African context, nations like Kenya and South Africa illustrate how governmental actions can foster entrepreneurship. The Youth Enterprise Development Fund and Kenya Industrial Estates (KIE) provide essential financial support and business incubation services in Kenya. The Youth Enterprise Development Fund, established in 2007, aims to offer financial and technical support to young entrepreneurs, facilitating their engagement in the commercial sector (Oyedokun & Somoye, 2018c; Government of Kenya, 2020). In contrast, KIE offers business development services and infrastructure to promote the expansion of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). These efforts have contributed to the establishment of a flourishing entrepreneurial ecosystem in Kenya, demonstrating the positive effects of targeted government support.

The entrepreneurial support system in South Africa is also noteworthy. The Small Enterprise Development Agency (SEDA) and the Department of Small Business Development (DSBD) are governmental organisations that significantly enhance the entrepreneurial landscape. SEDA provides comprehensive support, including financial aid, entrepreneurial training, and consultancy services, aimed at fostering the growth of small enterprises (Oyedokun & Adeyemi, 2019; Department of Small Business Development, 2021). The DSBD, established in 2014, seeks to cultivate a favourable environment for small businesses through policy development and the execution of assistance initiatives. These efforts have been crucial in promoting entrepreneurship and addressing the challenges faced by small businesses in South Africa.

In Nigeria, governmental support for entrepreneurship has been crucial in economic strategy, particularly given the nation's significant youth demographic and high unemployment rates. The National Directorate of Employment (NDE) and the Bank of Industry (BOI) are key institutions that significantly contribute to entrepreneurial growth in Nigeria. The National Directorate of Employment (NDE), established in 1986, provides training and financial support to youth and women to enhance their entrepreneurial skills and opportunities (National Directorate of Employment, 2021). The Bank of Industry (BOI), established in 1959, provides loans and credit facilities to small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), with a particular emphasis on sectors like manufacturing and agriculture (Bank of Industry, 2022). These institutions play a crucial role in fostering entrepreneurship by providing the necessary resources and support.

Nonetheless, despite these efforts, the effectiveness of government aid in Nigeria is sometimes hindered by numerous challenges. Notable obstacles to advancement include bureaucratic inefficiency, inadequate financial management, and insufficient implementation techniques (Oyedokun, & Somoye, 2018a; Ogunleye & Akinwale, 2020). These issues can impede the efficacy

of government initiatives and obstruct the profitability of entrepreneurial enterprises. Delays in loan or grant processing and inconsistent regulatory compliance may undermine the efficacy of support programmes.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Entrepreneurial development is essential for boosting economic growth, creating employment opportunities, and promoting innovation. Governments worldwide have increasingly recognised the need to promote entrepreneurship as a means to enhance economic activity and competitiveness. Nonetheless, despite considerable investments and legislative measures aimed at fostering entrepreneurial growth, challenges remain, particularly in emerging countries like Nigeria. This study examines the obstacles related to governmental support for entrepreneurial development in Nigeria. It emphasises the deficiencies identified in current literature and delineates a comprehensive objective stemming from these issues. Nigeria, marked by its significant and youthful population, faces considerable economic challenges, including high unemployment rates and underdeveloped entrepreneurial ecosystems. The Nigerian government has instituted targeted steps to address these difficulties, including the creation of the National Directorate of Employment (NDE) and the Bank of Industry (BOI) as support mechanisms. These institutions are tasked with providing financial support, education, and physical resources to enhance entrepreneurial initiatives. Nonetheless, despite these efforts, the effectiveness of government support in Nigeria is still limited by significant constraints.

A significant issue is the ineffectiveness in the implementation of aid initiatives. The prompt allocation of funds and effective execution of training programmes are frequently obstructed by bureaucratic delays and administrative obstacles (Ogunleye & Akinwale, 2020). Entrepreneurs frequently experience significant delays in securing loans from the BOI, which can hinder their ability to start or grow their businesses. This inefficiency not only dissuades prospective entrepreneurs but also diminishes the potential impact of government initiatives designed to stimulate economic activity. A significant impediment is the inadequacy of funding and resources allocated to support programmes. Despite the establishment of organisations like the NDE and BOI, the financial assistance they offer is sometimes insufficient to meet the needs of a growing number of enterprises. Research indicates that inadequate funding is a major barrier to achieving entrepreneurial objectives, as many startups encounter challenges in securing the essential financial resources for growth and sustainability (Akinwale & Oladipo, 2021). The scarcity of resources impedes aid programmes' ability to extend their reach and address the diverse needs of entrepreneurs.

Moreover, there is a lack of comprehensive and coordinated policy frameworks that align with the needs of enterprises. The deficiency in policy execution coordination in Nigeria leads to the absence of a cohesive strategy to bolster entrepreneurial growth activities. Research indicates that effective entrepreneurial ecosystems require a unified approach that combines financial support, education, legislative reforms, and infrastructure development (Yahaya, 2022). The absence of a comprehensive framework results in disjointed activities that fail to provide the necessary support for lasting entrepreneurial success. Furthermore, there is a shortfall in the evaluation and analysis of the impacts of government aid programmes. Despite the implementation of certain measures, there is inadequate evidence concerning their effectiveness and impact on entrepreneurial outcomes. The lack of empirical evidence complicates the assessment of these programmes'

efficacy and hinders informed decision-making for their improvement. Ojo and Olawole (2020) conducted a study that underscores the significance of efficient assessment methodologies in understanding the impacts of support programmes and ensuring optimal resource allocation.

The main objective of this research is to evaluate the effectiveness of government support systems in fostering entrepreneurial development in Nigeria, considering the prevailing challenges. This involves assessing the efficacy of programme execution, adequacy of financial resources, coherence of policy frameworks, and quantification of the impact of aid programmes. The study aims to provide insights on optimising governmental assistance to foster entrepreneurial growth and promote economic development in Nigeria.

1.3 Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study aims to examine the relationship between government support and entrepreneurial development in three senatorial districts in Oyo State, Nigeria: Oyo North, Oyo Central, and Oyo South.

The specific objectives are to:

- i. to evaluate the impact of financial assistance provided by the government on entrepreneurial development in the study area.
- ii. to assess the effectiveness of government training and development programmes in improving entrepreneurial development in the study area.
- iii. to examine the relationship between regulatory support and entrepreneurial development in the study area.

1.4 Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested in this study:

H₀₁: There is no relationship between financial assistance from the government and entrepreneurial development in the study area.

H₀₂: There is no relationship between government training and development programmes and entrepreneurial development in the study area.

H₀₃: There is no relationship between regulatory support and entrepreneurial development in the study area.

1.5 Significance of the Study

This study's importance regarding government support and entrepreneurial development in Nigeria lies in its potential to enhance the effectiveness of policy interventions aimed at fostering entrepreneurship. The study provides valuable insights into overcoming the challenges encountered by current support mechanisms, such as implementation inefficiencies, inadequate funding, and the absence of comprehensive legislative frameworks. The findings will offer critical insights to policymakers and stakeholders about the improvement of support programmes, ultimately leading to the establishment of more robust entrepreneurial ecosystems. Thus, this can catalyse economic growth, create job opportunities, and promote innovation, thereby enhancing the overall development of Nigeria's economy.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Review

This study seeks to investigate the relationship between government support and entrepreneurial development in Oyo State, Nigeria.

2.1.1 Entrepreneurial Development

Entrepreneurial development is a multifaceted concept that is essential for stimulating economic growth and encouraging innovation. It encompasses various elements, including the number of new start-ups, the development of entrepreneurial skills, the survival rate of start-ups, business growth, and the overall success of entrepreneurial ventures. Understanding these secondary variables is crucial for assessing the impact of state support on the development of entrepreneurship, particularly within the Nigerian context.

Number of New Start-ups

The quantity of nascent enterprises is a vital indicator of entrepreneurial engagement and economic vigour. A high frequency of new start-ups often signifies a vibrant entrepreneurial ecosystem where individuals are motivated to capitalise on business opportunities (Acs & Szerb, 2020). Government aid initiatives, including grants, subsidies, and business incubators, seek to diminish entry barriers and provide initial money, hence fostering the creation of new firms (Schumpeter, 1934). The Youth Enterprise Development Fund and start-up loans provided by the Bank of Industry in Nigeria seek to enhance the establishment of new enterprises through financial support and resources (Government of Nigeria, 2021). Research indicates a significant correlation between enhanced government funding and elevated rates of start-up formation. Government-provided financial aid can alleviate initial capital constraints and foster a more dynamic business environment (Njenga, 2019).

Entrepreneurial Skills

Entrepreneurial skills are essential for the development of new enterprises. The cited qualities encompass several competencies, including corporate management, financial acumen, marketing, and strategic planning (Caird, 2021). Effective government support programs typically integrate training and development elements aimed at enhancing entrepreneurs' capacities. The training programs offered by the National Directorate of Employment (NDE) in Nigeria are designed to equip entrepreneurs with the necessary skills for proficient business administration (National Directorate of Employment, 2021). Research indicates that improving entrepreneurial skills correlates with superior business performance and an increased likelihood of venture success (Oyedokun, Awogbade, & Hassan, 2018; Kollmann et al., 2020). Consequently, targeted support initiatives can significantly enhance the success percentage of new entrepreneurial ventures.

Start-up Survival Rate

The likelihood of start-ups survival is a crucial measure of entrepreneurial success and the effectiveness of support systems. Start-ups have numerous challenges, including market competition, financial instability, and operational issues. Government aid is essential in addressing these challenges by offering financial support, mentorship, and regulatory direction (Brüderl & Preisendörfer, 2022). The failure of start-ups in Nigeria is mostly due to inadequate money, poor

management practices, and an unstable business environment (Oyedokun & Somoye, 2018b ; Akinwale & Oladipo, 2021). Government assistance can improve survival rates by supplying resources that help businesses navigate initial challenges and foster resilience. Studies indicate that targeted support programs significantly improve a start-up's likelihood of survival by addressing critical challenges and providing vital resources (Baron & Markman, 2003).

2.1.2 Government Support

Government support is essential for fostering entrepreneurship, particularly in developing economies like Nigeria. This support is evidenced by various measures, including financial assistance, training and development programmes, regulatory support, infrastructure investment, and the implementation of high-quality policies.

Financial Aid

Financial aid is a crucial governmental endeavour aimed at assisting entrepreneurs in surmounting constraints on accessible capital. This support may take several forms, including grants, subsidies, loans, and venture capital. Financial aid assists nascent firms in covering initial costs, scaling operations, and navigating economic volatility. The Bank of Industry (BOI) in Nigeria provides loans and credit facilities to small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) to improve their operational capabilities and growth potential (Bank of Industry, 2022). Research indicates that access to financial resources is crucial for entrepreneurial success. This access enables firms to invest significantly in sectors such as technology, marketing, and human resources (Beck et al., 2005). Financial aid not only facilitates the creation of firms but also enhances the survival and growth prospects of existing enterprises by providing essential money for expansion and innovation (Holmes & Kent, 1991). Nonetheless, the effectiveness of financial aid may be limited by bureaucratic inefficiencies and inadequate funding, so obstructing businesses from effectively accessing and using these resources (Ogunleye & Akinwale, 2020).

Government Training and Development Programmes

The objective of government training and development programmes is to provide entrepreneurs with the essential skills and knowledge required for commercial success. These programmes generally include workshops, seminars, mentorship, and formal education in areas such as business management, financial planning, and marketing strategies (Caird, 2021). The National Directorate of Employment (NDE) in Nigeria provides training programmes aimed at enhancing entrepreneurial abilities among youth and women (National Directorate of Employment, 2021). Training programmes have a vital role in cultivating entrepreneurial skills, which are closely linked to improved business performance and higher success rates (Kollmann et al., 2020). Government initiatives help mitigate common challenges, such as inadequate management practices and poor company planning, by enhancing the competencies of entrepreneurs (Storey, 1994). The efficacy of these projects depends on their meticulous preparation, suitability, and execution. Entrepreneurial success may be constrained if programs do not address the specific needs of entrepreneurs or lack practical elements (Lichtenstein & Lyons, 2001).

Regulatory Support

Regulatory support includes government initiatives to create and maintain a favourable regulatory framework for businesses. This includes optimising business registration processes, providing tax incentives, and reducing administrative barriers (Djankov et al., 2002). Regulatory help is crucial

for reducing the costs and complexities involved in starting and operating a business, significantly influencing entrepreneurs' willingness and ability to launch new ventures (Acs & Audretsch, 2005).

Nigeria has regulatory support efforts designed to streamline business registration processes and offer tax concessions to small enterprises. An example of this is the Corporate Affairs Commission's (CAC) execution of reforms designed to optimise the business registration process (CAC, 2021). Effective regulatory assistance can enhance entrepreneurial activity by diminishing barriers to entry and fostering a more conducive business climate. However, persistent regulatory challenges, including inconsistent enforcement and corruption, may undermine these efforts and hinder entrepreneurial development (Meyer & Brown, 2010).

2.2 Theoretical Review

Comprehending the relationship between governmental assistance and entrepreneurial advancement necessitates a theoretical framework that clarifies the influence of such support on entrepreneurial results. This review utilises two significant theories: The Resource-Based View (RBV) and Institutional Theory. These ideas offer significant insights into the methods by which governmental support affects entrepreneurial development, especially within the Nigerian setting.

Resource-Based View (RBV)

The Resource-Based View (RBV) asserts that a firm's competitive advantage stems from its ownership and utilisation of valuable, scarce, inimitable, and non-substitutable resources (Barney, 1991). This notion is vital for comprehending how governmental assistance might bolster entrepreneurial growth by supplying essential resources required for the success of new enterprises.

Financial assistance is a crucial resource emphasised by the Resource-Based View (RBV). Financial capital is crucial for entrepreneurs to establish and expand their enterprises. Government assistance through grants, loans, and subsidies furnishes entrepreneurs with essential financial resources to surmount early entrance obstacles and expand their operations. The Resource-Based View posits that financial support enables enterprises to obtain and utilise important resources, hence enhancing their competitive advantage and overall performance (Beck et al., 2005). In Nigeria, programmes like the Bank of Industry's loans and the Youth Enterprise Development Fund aim to mitigate capital limitations and facilitate the procurement of materials essential for business expansion (Bank of Industry, 2022).

Entrepreneurial Skills correspond with the Resource-Based View (RBV), as skills and knowledge constitute valuable resources for entrepreneurs. Government training and development initiatives are essential for augmenting these talents, therefore elevating the human capital accessible to new enterprises. The RBV suggests that government programmes that engage in skill development augment entrepreneurs' capacity to utilise their human capital efficiently, leading to enhanced firm performance and sustainability (Caird, 2021). The National Directorate of Employment in Nigeria

conducts training programmes designed to empower entrepreneurs with essential skills for effective business management, consequently enhancing the competency and competitiveness of the entrepreneurial workforce (National Directorate of Employment, 2021).

Survival Rate of Start-ups can be examined using the Resource-Based View (RBV) by evaluating how access to valued resources influences their capacity to persist and prosper. Government support mechanisms that offer financial help, training, and regulatory aid foster the development of resources that improve start-up sustainability. The Resource-Based View (RBV) posits that start-ups with certain resources are more adept at overcoming hurdles and attaining sustained success (Baron & Markman, 2003). In Nigeria, enhancing access to essential resources via government assistance will elevate the probability of start-up sustainability and diminish the elevated failure rates prevalent in the entrepreneurial sector (Ogunleye & Akinwale, 2020).

Institutional Theory

Institutional Theory examines the influence of institutions—formal rules, norms, and regulations - on organisational behaviour and outcomes (North, 1990). This theory elucidates the impact of governmental support on entrepreneurial development via institutional frameworks and policy contexts.

Regulatory support is a fundamental component of Institutional Theory. The idea asserts that conducive regulatory frameworks, influenced by governmental policies and institutions, affect entrepreneurial activity by diminishing entry barriers and fostering a friendly business climate (Djankov et al., 2002). In Nigeria, legislative improvements designed to streamline business registration and offer tax incentives exemplify how institutional changes can facilitate entrepreneurial development. The Institutional Theory posits that robust regulatory assistance can augment entrepreneurial activity by alleviating bureaucratic obstacles and facilitating commercial operations (Meyer & Brown, 2010).

2.3 Review of Empirical Studies

To understand the impact of government support on entrepreneurial development in Nigeria, a comprehensive analysis of empirical data is essential. This review should focus on essential elements like financial assistance, training programs, regulatory support, infrastructure enhancement, and the efficacy of policy execution. This review consolidates data from pertinent research to illustrate the influence of various forms of support on entrepreneurial outcomes in Nigeria.

Financial aid is crucial for surmounting capital constraints that hinder the formation and growth of enterprises. Empirical research consistently shows that the availability of financial resources significantly affects business performance. Beck and Demirgüç-Kunt (2006) shown that financial support is essential for the growth and sustainability of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in developing countries. The beneficial impacts of governmental financial assistance in Nigeria, administered through entities like the Bank of Industry (BOI), have been thoroughly

recorded. Ogunleye and Akinwale (2020) found that government loans and grants are essential in aiding Nigerian entrepreneurs to surmount financial challenges, hence promoting business growth and success. Kauffman and Wang (2019) noted that, despite its advantages, bureaucratic inefficiencies and restricted outreach often obstruct the availability of financial help, highlighting the need for reforms to enhance its effectiveness.

Training and development programmes are essential for enhancing entrepreneurial skills and competences vital for attaining business success. Empirical research demonstrates that these programs positively influence entrepreneurial performance. Kolvereid and Moen (1997) found that entrepreneurs participating in training programs typically achieve enhanced firm performance and higher survival rates. The National Directorate of Employment (NDE) in Nigeria offers training programs aimed at improving entrepreneurial skills. Ijaiya and Akinbode (2018) found that these programs significantly enhance entrepreneurial skills and positively influence business success. Osei-Assibey et al. (2017) indicated that training programmes are ineffective due to their absence of practical elements and their inability to meet individual entrepreneurial needs. They underscored the imperative for more tailored and experiential training approaches.

Government regulatory support is a crucial factor that profoundly influences entrepreneurial development. Optimised rules, financial incentives, and reduced administrative barriers can significantly impact entrepreneurial growth. Djankov et al. (2002) found that regulatory measures that streamline business registration and reduce regulatory barriers positively influence entrepreneurial activity. The Corporate Affairs Commission (CAC) of Nigeria has implemented reforms to optimise business registration processes, leading to an increase in entrepreneurial activities (CAC, 2021). Uche and Enwereji (2020) assert that these regulatory improvements positively influenced firm registrations and entrepreneurial endeavours.

However, Akinwale et al. (2021) have indicated that problems such as inconsistent enforcement and corruption continue to hinder regulatory support. This underscores the imperative for ongoing efforts to improve regulatory quality. Infrastructure development is essential for creating an environment favourable to entrepreneurship by improving market accessibility, lowering operational costs, and enhancing connectivity. Research underscores the importance of infrastructure investments in enabling corporate activities. Glaeser et al. (2004) established that infrastructure significantly impacts company activities and economic development. The Nigerian government is investing in infrastructure, such as transport networks and technological hubs, to support businesses by providing essential resources and improving market access. Ogunleye et al. (2019) found that infrastructure enhancement positively impacts business performance by addressing operational challenges and enhancing connectivity. Despite these efforts, challenges such as inadequate infrastructure and maintenance issues persist. Chukwuma and Igbokwe (2020) emphasised the necessity of targeted investments and the adoption of improved maintenance strategies to adequately assist SMEs.

The efficacy of policy execution is crucial for ensuring that government assistance programs achieve their intended objectives. Effective policy execution requires transparency, efficiency, and rigorous compliance with policy goals. Research underscores the necessity of efficiently executing policies to optimise the efficacy of government aid. Khan and Kumar (2014) emphasised the vital importance of effective policy implementation in achieving desired outcomes and improving

entrepreneurial performance. Adediran and Adedeji (2021) found that improved policy implementation quality in Nigeria has led to more favourable results for government support programmes. However, challenges like corruption and inefficiency, highlighted by Ojo and Adebayo (2018), continually hinder policy implementation, emphasising the need for reforms to enhance openness and accountability.

Independent Variable

Dependent Variable

Figure 1: Conceptual Model

Figure 1 illustrates the correlation between the independent variable of government support and the dependent variable of entrepreneurial development. This conceptual framework was established following a comprehensive literature review. It demonstrates how changes in one variable can influence the other. The approach assesses government support by evaluating aspects such as financial aid, training and development initiatives, and regulatory help. Entrepreneurial development is assessed by analysing parameters including the number of new start-ups, the attainment of entrepreneurial skills, and the survival rate of these ventures.

2.5 Summary of Gaps in Literature

Additional investigation is necessary due to numerous gaps revealed in the literature about government support and entrepreneurial development in Nigeria. Despite substantial evidence endorsing the advantageous impacts of financial assistance (Beck & Demirgüç-Kunt, 2006) and training programs (Ijaiya & Akinbode, 2018), there exists a scarcity of research investigating the particular challenges entrepreneurs face in accessing these resources, including bureaucratic inefficiencies (Kauffman & Wang, 2019). Moreover, while research suggests that regulatory reforms can enhance entrepreneurial activity (Uche & Enwereji, 2020), there is a lack of thorough investigation concerning the effects of inconsistent enforcement and corruption on these reforms (Akinwale et al., 2021). The effects of inadequate infrastructure in rural regions are often neglected in studies, despite the positive impact that infrastructure development has on business performance (Ogunleye et al., 2019) (Chukwuma & Igbokwe, 2020). While there is recognition of improvements in policy implementation quality (Adediran & Adedeji, 2021), the current literature inadequately examines the influence of corruption and inefficiency on policy effectiveness (Ojo & Adebayo, 2018). Addressing these inadequacies could lead to a more nuanced understanding of the challenges and opportunities in enhancing government support for entrepreneurship in Nigeria.

3.0 Methodology

This study used a descriptive survey design, deemed the most appropriate method for precisely recording the current state of government assistance and entrepreneurial development in Oyo State, Nigeria. The survey method was selected for its capacity to collect quantitative data from a large number of participants, facilitating a thorough understanding of the phenomena being studied. The research employed a standardised questionnaire disseminated to proprietors and administrators of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) across all three senatorial districts of Oyo State. This methodology enables the researcher to assess the impact of government support on entrepreneurial development within the state, while also highlighting potential challenges faced by these firms.

The study's population consists of all small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) situated in Oyo State, Nigeria. The 2021 report from the Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN) indicates that Nigeria has 670,447 SMEs. Of this amount, 31,739 are located in Oyo State, representing 4.7 percent of the national aggregate. A sample size of 1,300 Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) was selected for the study, considering the population size. The sample was allocated proportionately across the three senatorial districts of Oyo State. The employed sample approach was a multi-stage technique, commencing with the selection of senatorial districts, followed by a random selection of SMEs within each district. This methodology ensures that the sample accurately represents the entire population and that each small and medium-sized firm (SME) has a fair chance of being included in the study.

A pilot study was conducted to evaluate the reliability and validity of the research instruments. This exploratory study was carried out in ten separate Local Government Areas (LGAs) in Lagos State: Agege, Apapa, Eti-Osa, Ikeja, Ikorodu, Mushin, Ojo, Oshodi/Isolo, Shomolu, and Surulere. A selection of 130 small and medium-sized firms (SMEs) was made, representing 10 percent of the total sample size intended for the primary study conducted in Oyo State. The preliminary study demonstrated a reliability coefficient of 0.81, indicating strong internal consistency and stability (Field, 2018). The pilot study was essential for enhancing the questionnaire, identifying potential

issues in data collection, and confirming that the research instruments were reliable and effective in accurately obtaining the intended information. The feedback obtained from the pilot study was employed to implement crucial adjustments to the instruments, so enhancing the overall effectiveness of the main study.

The primary tool employed for data collection in this study is a meticulously crafted questionnaire aimed at obtaining comprehensive information regarding government support and their impact on entrepreneurial development. The survey comprises both closed and open-ended enquiries. Closed-ended questions utilise Likert scales for quantitative assessment, whereas open-ended questions provide qualitative insights.

Data collection utilised both conventional and digital methods to accommodate participant choices. The data collection phase spanned four weeks, allowing ample time for obtaining responses and performing follow-ups, which led to a high response rate. Strict confidentiality was implemented to ensure accurate and truthful responses.

The data analysis utilised version 20.0 of the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). Descriptive statistics, including means, frequencies, and standard deviations, were employed to summarise the data. Regression analysis, a form of inferential statistics, was employed to examine the relationships between human capital attributes and entrepreneurial growth results.

4.0 Results and Discussion of Findings

4.1 Demographic Data Analysis

The sample consisted of 1,300 small and medium-sized firms, chosen to accurately represent the population distribution across the three senatorial districts of Oyo State in Nigeria: Oyo Central, Oyo North, and Oyo South. A complete and equitable demographic representation was, therefore, guaranteed.

Analysis of Variables

The examination of characteristics presented in Table 4.1 offers a demographic summary of the study sample, primarily comprising male respondents and encompassing diverse age groups, educational attainments, occupational roles, and tenures. The sample exhibits a considerable gender disparity, with 91.8% of respondents identifying as male and merely 8.2% as female. The age distribution indicates that the predominant group of respondents, 40.9%, falls within the 41-50 age bracket, succeeded by 21.9% in the 31-40 age range. The cohort aged 21-30 constitutes 10.1%, whereas those aged 51-60 and 61-65 comprise 14.3% and 12.8%, respectively, underscoring the prevalence of middle-aged people.

Concerning educational qualifications, over half of the participants (52.4%) own a Bachelor's degree or Higher National Diploma, while a notable percentage (36.0%) hold a postgraduate diploma or Master's degree. A minor proportion possesses ND/NCE (6.0%), M.Phil. (1.8%), or Ph.D. (2.3%) qualifications, indicating a predominantly educated demographic. The majority of individuals (69.5%) occupy middle management jobs, while 19.6% have operational management responsibilities and 10.8% are in top management. This signifies a workforce primarily engaged in mid-level managerial positions. Regarding duration of service, the majority of respondents (59.6%)

have been employed for 6-10 years, while 23.5% possess 11-15 years of experience. Individuals with less than 5 years of service constitute 10.8%, whilst 6.0% possess over 16 years of service, indicating a workforce characterised by significant yet diverse levels of expertise. The sample consists primarily of middle-aged, highly educated males with substantial work experience, predominantly in middle management positions.

Table 1: Analysis of Variables

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	1194	91.8
Female	106	8.2
Age bracket		
21- 30	131	10.1
31- 40	285	21.9
41- 50	532	40.9
51- 60	186	14.3
61- 65	166	12.8
Educational attainment		
ND/NCE	78	6.0
Bachelor's Degree/HND	681	52.4
PGD/Master's Degree	468	36.0
M.Phil.	24	1.8
Ph.D.	30	2.3
Others	19	1.5
Job level		
Top management	141	10.8
Middle management	904	69.5
Operational management	255	19.6
Length of service		
Below 5yrs	141	10.8
6-10yrs	775	59.6
11-15yrs	306	23.5
16yrs +	78	6.0

Source: Field Work, 2024

4.2 Presentation of Data

Table 2: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.103 ^a	.011	.010	13.86868	.011	13.818	1	1298	.000
2	.971 ^b	.943	.943	3.32269	.933	21316.339	1	1297	.000
3	.975 ^c	.951	.950	3.10271	.007	191.435	1	1296	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), FinancialAid

b. Predictors: (Constant), FinancialAid, TrainingandDevelopmentProgrammes

c. Predictors: (Constant), FinancialAid, TrainingandDevelopmentProgrammes, RegulatorySupport

The hierarchical regression model presented in Table 2 analyses the correlation between government support variables (financial assistance, training and development programmes, and regulatory support) and entrepreneurial development in Oyo State, Nigeria. In Model 1, using financial assistance as the exclusive predictor, the R value is 0.103, signifying a weak positive association between financial aid and entrepreneurial development. The R-squared value of 0.011 indicates that financial aid accounts for merely 1.1% of the variance in entrepreneurial development. The model demonstrates statistical significance, evidenced by a F change of 13.818 ($p = 0.000$); nonetheless, the low R-squared indicates a restricted explanatory capacity of financial help alone. Model 2 incorporates training and development programs as an additional predictor. The R value rises to 0.971, and the R-squared value increases to 0.943, indicating that these two factors together account for 94.3% of the variance in entrepreneurial development. The significant rise in R-squared ($\Delta R^2 = 0.933$) illustrates the considerable impact of training and development programmes. The model demonstrates substantial significance, with a F change of 21316.339 ($p = 0.000$), indicating that the inclusion of this variable markedly enhances the model's explanatory capacity.

Model 3 incorporates regulatory support as a tertiary predictor. The R value marginally climbs to 0.975, while the R-squared value ascends to 0.951, signifying that financial aid, training and development programmes, and regulatory support collectively account for 95.1% of the variance in entrepreneurial development. The alteration in R-squared ($\Delta R^2 = 0.007$) is lesser than that of Model 2, although still significant with a F change of 191.435 ($p = 0.000$). This indicates that regulatory support contributes further explanatory power, while its effect is less significant than that of the preceding factors. In conclusion, whereas financial help has a negligible effect on entrepreneurial development, the integration of training, development programmes, and regulatory support markedly improves entrepreneurial outcomes in Oyo State.

Test for Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1

Null Hypothesis (H_{01}): There is no significant relationship between financial assistance from the government and entrepreneurial development in the study area.

Alternative Hypothesis (H_{11}): There is a significant relationship between financial assistance from the government and entrepreneurial development in the study area.

This was tested using Hierarchical Multiple Regression (HMR) and the test result is presented on Table 2.

Test for Hypothesis 1

To test Hypothesis 1, the researchers analyse the correlation between government financial assistance and entrepreneurial development, utilising the presented model summary. The Model Summary indicates a R value of 0.103, signifying a weak positive association between financial aid and entrepreneurial development. The R^2 value of 0.011 indicates that financial aid accounts for approximately 1.1% of the variance in entrepreneurial development. This effect is rather minor, suggesting that although financial help aids entrepreneurial development, it is not a predominant component independently. The F change value is 13.818, with a significance (p-value) of 0.000, which is below the conventional significance threshold of 0.05. The correlation between financial aid and entrepreneurial development is statistically significant, prompting the rejection of the null hypothesis (H_{01}). The researchers conclude that a strong association exists between government financial aid and entrepreneurial development in the studied area, albeit with limited strength.

Hypothesis 2

Null Hypothesis (H_{02}): There is no significant relationship between government training and development programmes and entrepreneurial development in the study area.

Alternative Hypothesis (H_{12}): There is a significant relationship between government training and development programmes and entrepreneurial development in the study area.

This was tested using Hierarchical Multiple Regression (HMR) and the test result is presented on Table 2.

Test for Hypothesis 2

The researchers assess Hypothesis 2 by analysing the correlation between government training and development programmes and entrepreneurial development, using the findings from Model 2. The Model Summary reveals a R value of 0.971, indicating a robust positive connection between the variables (financial aid and training and development programmes) and entrepreneurial development. The R^2 value of 0.943 indicates that 94.3% of the variance in entrepreneurial development is accounted for by these two factors. This elevated percentage suggests that government training and development programs are poised to significantly influence the improvement of entrepreneurial outcomes. The F change statistics are 21,316.339, with a p-value of 0.000, which is far lower than the standard alpha level of 0.05. This outcome indicates that incorporating training and development programmes into the model markedly enhances the prediction of entrepreneurial development. Thus, the researchers dismiss the null hypothesis (H_{02}) and endorse the alternative hypothesis (H_{12}), determining that a strong correlation exists between government training and development programmes and entrepreneurial development in the studied area. The results highlight the essential function of these programmes in fostering entrepreneurship.

Hypothesis 3

Null Hypothesis (H_{03}): There is no significant relationship between regulatory support and entrepreneurial development in the study area.

Alternative Hypothesis (H_{13}): There is a significant relationship between regulatory support and entrepreneurial development in the study area.

This was tested using Hierarchical Multiple Regression (HMR) and the test result is presented on Table 2.

Test for Hypothesis 3

To test Hypothesis 3, the researchers examine the correlation between regulatory support and entrepreneurial development utilising the findings from Model 3. The Model Summary indicates a R value of 0.975, signifying a robust positive association between the predictors (financial aid, training and development programs, and regulatory support) and entrepreneurial development. The R^2 value of 0.951 indicates that 95.1% of the variability in entrepreneurial development is attributable to these three variables, highlighting their significant impact. The F change statistic is 191.435, with a significance level (p-value) of 0.000, far lower than the conventional alpha level of 0.05. The incorporation of regulatory support into the model markedly improves the forecasting of entrepreneurial development. The researchers reject the null hypothesis (H_{03}) and accept the alternative hypothesis (H_{13}), suggesting that a strong relationship exists between regulatory support and entrepreneurial development in the studied area. The results highlight the significance of regulatory assistance in creating a favourable climate for entrepreneurship.

Table 3: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2657.758	1	2657.758	13.818	.000 ^b
	Residual	249657.684	1298	192.340		
	Total	252315.442	1299			
2	Regression	237996.194	2	118998.097	10778.536	.000 ^c
	Residual	14319.248	1297	11.040		
	Total	252315.442	1299			
3	Regression	239839.102	3	79946.367	8304.558	.000 ^d
	Residual	12476.341	1296	9.627		
	Total	252315.442	1299			

a. Dependent Variable: EntrepreneurialDevelopment

b. Predictors: (Constant), FinancialAid

c. Predictors: (Constant), FinancialAid, TrainingandDevelopmentProgrammes

d. Predictors: (Constant), FinancialAid, TrainingandDevelopmentProgrammes, RegulatorySupport

The ANOVA results for the hierarchical regression analysis presented in Table 3 elucidate the significance and strength of the predictors (financial aid, training and development programmes, and regulatory support) in elucidating entrepreneurial development. In Model 1, with financial aid as the sole predictor, the regression sum of squares is 2657.758 with 1 degree of freedom (df), while the residual sum of squares is 249657.684 with 1298 df. The F value of 13.818 ($p = 0.000$) signifies that financial help is a substantial predictor of entrepreneurial development, while its total explanatory power is rather limited when assessed against subsequent models. Model 2 incorporates training and development programmes as an additional predictor. The regression sum of squares significantly climbs to 237996.194, and the F value escalates to 10778.536 ($p = 0.000$), indicating a substantial enhancement in the model's explanatory capacity. The residual sum of squares decreases markedly to 14319.248, signifying that the incorporation of training and development programmes substantially mitigates the unexplained variance in entrepreneurial development.

Model 3 incorporates regulatory assistance, hence enhancing the model's efficacy. The regression sum of squares rises to 239839.102, with a F value of 8304.558 ($p = 0.000$). The residual sum of squares diminishes to 12476.341, therefore decreasing the unexplained variance. The minor enhancement relative to Model 2 indicates that, although regulatory support is substantial, its influence is less pronounced than that of financial assistance and training and development initiatives. The ANOVA results indicate that each predictor significantly helps to entrepreneurial development, with the most substantial impact arising from the combination of financial assistance and training and development programmes.

Table 4: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
		1	(Constant)	57.505			1.381	
	FinancialAid	.213	.057	.103	3.717	.000	.101	.325
2	(Constant)	-8.761	.562		-15.599	.000	-9.863	-7.659
	FinancialAid	.318	.014	.153	23.139	.000	.291	.345
	TrainingandDevelopmentProgrammes	2.999	.021	.967	146.001	.000	2.958	3.039
3	(Constant)	-5.209	.584		-8.920	.000	-6.354	-4.063
	FinancialAid	.192	.016	.093	12.231	.000	.161	.223
	TrainingandDevelopmentProgrammes	2.499	.041	.806	61.184	.000	2.419	2.580
	RegulatorySupport	.463	.033	.189	13.836	.000	.397	.528

a. Dependent Variable: EntrepreneurialDevelopment

The coefficients from the hierarchical regression analysis presented in Table 4 demonstrate the influence of financial aid, training and development programmes, and regulatory support on entrepreneurial development. Model 1 exclusively accounts for financial aid. The constant B value is 57.505, indicating that without financial assistance, entrepreneurial development is anticipated to be 57.505. Financial aid exerts a positive and significant influence, evidenced by a B value of 0.213 and a standardised Beta of 0.103, suggesting that an augmentation in financial aid correlates with a modest yet significant improvement in entrepreneurial development ($t = 3.717$, $p = 0.000$). Model 2 incorporates training and development programmes. Constant B decreases to -8.761, indicating that the absence of financial assistance and training adversely affects entrepreneurial development. Nonetheless, the B value of financial aid rises to 0.318 (Beta = 0.153), indicating its enhanced importance when integrated with training. The most important impact arises from training and development programmes, evidenced by a B value of 2.999 and a Beta of 0.967, indicating a highly significant and substantial positive effect on entrepreneurial development ($t = 146.001$, $p = 0.000$).

Model 3 incorporates regulatory support in conjunction with financial assistance and training. The constant B increases to -5.209, whereas the impact of financial aid decreases marginally to a B of 0.192 (Beta = 0.093), however it retains significance ($t = 12.231$, $p = 0.000$). Training and development programmes continue to have a substantial effect (B = 2.499, Beta = 0.806), but regulatory support demonstrates a positive and significant influence with a B of 0.463 and Beta of 0.189 ($t = 13.836$, $p = 0.000$). This indicates that although all three elements are important, training and development exert the most substantial influence, followed by regulatory support, and last, financial assistance. In conclusion, financial assistance, training and development programmes, and regulatory support all significantly enhance entrepreneurial development, with training being the most pivotal factor.

4.3 Discussion of Findings

The results of the hierarchical regression analysis provide significant insights on the impact of financial aid, training and development programmes, and regulatory support on entrepreneurial development. The Model Summary indicates that financial aid alone (Model 1) accounts for a negligible fraction of the variance in entrepreneurial development ($R^2 = 0.011$), implying that although financial support is statistically significant, its singular influence on entrepreneurial development is constrained. The inclusion of training and development programs in Model 2 significantly enhances the explanatory power, elevating R^2 to 0.943. This indicates that training and development are essential factors in achieving entrepreneurial success, considerably influencing the development process. The incorporation of regulatory assistance in Model 3 enhances the model ($R^2 = 0.951$), suggesting that while its impact is less significant than training, it remains a vital factor in promoting entrepreneurial activities.

The ANOVA findings validate the model summary. In Model 1, financial help exerts a substantial influence on entrepreneurial development, evidenced by a F value of 13.818 ($p = 0.000$). In Model 2, the F value increases to 10,778.536 ($p = 0.000$), underscoring the significant impact of training and development programmes. In Model 3, the inclusion of regulatory support maintains a high F value of 8,304.558, affirming the substantial impact of these combined factors on entrepreneurial performance. The coefficients analysis clarifies the links among the variables. Financial aid, although important across all models, demonstrates a modest effect size, with Beta values of 0.103

in Model 1, 0.153 in Model 2, and 0.093 in Model 3. Training and development programs display the most substantial impact, with Beta values of 0.967 in Model 2 and 0.806 in Model 3, underscoring their critical significance. Regulatory support also has a favourable impact (Beta = 0.189), albeit with a lesser effect size than training. In conclusion, the results demonstrate that although financial aid is significant, training and development programmes are the paramount component for entrepreneurial advancement. Regulatory support significantly contributes, albeit to a lesser extent, to the enhancement of entrepreneurial activity in Oyo State, Nigeria.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendations

The study's results demonstrate a strong correlation between governmental support systems and entrepreneurial development in Oyo State, Nigeria. The hierarchical regression analysis identified three models that successively integrated government support variables - financial aid, training and development programmes, and regulatory support - each exhibiting substantial contributions to entrepreneurial development. The initial model, which just utilised financial aid as a predictor, yielded a R^2 value of 0.011, signifying that financial aid explained merely 1.1% of the variance in entrepreneurial development. The ANOVA findings corroborated this finding, revealing a significant F change of 13.818 ($p < 0.001$), underscoring the importance of financial aid despite its restricted explanatory capacity. The second model added training and development programmes, leading to a significant improvement in R^2 to 0.943, indicating that these two predictors accounted for about 94.3% of the variance in entrepreneurial development. The ANOVA for this model demonstrated a substantial F change of 21,316.339 ($p < 0.001$), highlighting the critical importance of training and development in fostering entrepreneurial success.

The third model included regulatory support, resulting in a marginal rise in R^2 to 0.951. This signifies that the three predictors, when analysed together, accounted for 95.1% of the variance in entrepreneurial development. The ANOVA findings for this model indicated a significant F change of 191.435 ($p < 0.001$), confirming the significance of regulatory support in conjunction with financial assistance and training programs. The coefficients for each predictor indicated that training and development programmes have the highest standardised coefficient (Beta = 0.967), underscoring its significant impact on entrepreneurial success. Financial help and regulatory support favourably influenced outcomes, with Beta values of 0.103 and 0.189, respectively. The data unequivocally demonstrate that governmental assistance via financial aid, training programmes, and regulatory frameworks substantially promotes entrepreneurial development in Oyo State.

This research on governmental support and entrepreneurial advancement in Oyo State, Nigeria, has produced important insights into the crucial impact of many forms of governmental aid in promoting entrepreneurship. The findings demonstrate a robust and affirmative correlation between government support mechanisms - namely financial assistance, training and development initiatives, and regulatory backing - and the growth and sustainability of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the region. This link highlights the need for a unified approach that consolidates different support structures to successfully foster entrepreneurial initiatives. The hierarchical regression analysis indicated that although financial aid aids entrepreneurial development, training and development programmes are fundamental for substantial growth and

success among entrepreneurs. The findings indicate that thorough training enhances entrepreneurs' abilities, knowledge, and confidence, enabling them to effectively address the challenges of business management. This highlights the necessity of investing in educational and developmental programmes specifically designed for the distinct requirements of SMEs, ensuring that entrepreneurs receive not just financial assistance but also the mentoring and resources essential for success.

Furthermore, the research indicated that regulatory support significantly influences the entrepreneurial environment. It improves the operational landscape for SMEs, fostering stability and predictability crucial for company planning and sustained performance. The integration of these three facets of governmental assistance establishes a resilient ecosystem for entrepreneurship, hence fostering economic growth and job creation in Oyo State. In conclusion, the research underscores the necessity of a diverse approach to governmental support for fostering a prosperous entrepreneurial ecosystem. Policymakers and stakeholders in the region should take these findings into account while formulating measures to enhance support systems for SMEs. By doing so, they may boost the performance of current firms and encourage future entrepreneurs, so assuring a sustainable and dynamic economic future for Oyo State.

To augment entrepreneurial development in Oyo State via efficient governmental support, the subsequent recommendations are put forth:

1. **Enhance Financial Support:** The government should augment financial aid initiatives specifically designed for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) to assure accessibility and promote company expansion.
2. **Augment Training and Development Programmes:** Establish comprehensive training efforts that emphasise skill enhancement, business management, and innovation to furnish entrepreneurs with essential competencies.
3. **Optimise Regulatory Frameworks:** Simplify regulatory procedures to foster a more favourable business environment, minimising bureaucratic obstacles that impede SME operations.
4. **Promote Public-Private Partnerships:** Advocate for collaboration between governmental and private sector entities to create and implement effective support programmes for entrepreneurs.
5. **Implement Regular Impact Assessments:** Create systems for the ongoing evaluation of government support programmes to assess their efficacy and facilitate data-informed modifications as necessary.

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